

THE SMART BLANKHOLDER AS A DEVELOPMENT TOOL FOR THE RUBBER FORMING PROCESS OF CONTINUOUS FIBER REINFORCED THERMOPLASTICS

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ABSTRACT

During the last decade thermoplastic composites have become more important for production of secondary aircraft structures. There is a tendency of replacing thermoset parts by thermoplastics, due to their cost-effective manufacturing methods.

Cetex™ laminates (glass, carbon or aramid fiber reinforced PPS or PEI; Ten Cate Advanced Composites) are semi-manufactured articles with a consumer dependent build-up. The laminates can be processed by means of a thermoforming process. One of these processes is rubber forming of continuous fiber reinforced thermoplastics. A laminate is cut into blanks after which a blank is heated in an infrared oven. Once the process temperature of the material is reached, the blank is transported into a press, where the blank is formed between a rubber die and a metal die.

During the forming step in the press, two mechanisms dominate fabric deformations. The first mechanism is intra-ply shearing: the fibers in each separate layer shear with respect to each other. The second mechanism is inter-ply slip. Shearing angles can easily be predicted by the fabric draping software tool "Drape". Fabrics with different orientations can be draped over a die to determine the shearing angles. For different types of fabrics, the critical shearing angle changes.

The critical shearing angle in fact gives the maximum deformation of the fabric, before wrinkling, buckling or tearing occurs. However, with the use of a blankholder, increased fabric deformations may be realised without wrinkling. Conventional blankholders use springs, the blankholder described in this paper consists of pneumatic actuators. This has advantages compared to conventional blankholders:

- Blankholder forces can be computer controlled (controlling the fiber tension).
- Heating is more homogeneous: during heating the fabric will be kept under tension and remain flat. Since double-sided heating is used, this means the distance to the upper and lower infrared heater will remain equal.
- Reduction of the time-span of the trial and error trajectory, preliminary to production of a new product.
- Ease of handling.

In order to investigate the influence of the use of a blankholder on critical fabric deformations, a die of a military helmet has been used, wherein different shearing angles will occur, according to a Drape analysis. The influence of the blankholder, existing of 10 movable, pneumatic cylinders with a force range of 90 - 720 N each, was tested on an 8H satin glass fabric with a PPS matrix. Though some improvements were made, the blankholder is still under development.

KEY TERMS: Rubber forming, helmet, fabric, blankholder, clamps.

INTRODUCTION

Rubber forming of continuous fiber reinforced thermoplastics is a fast and reproducible production method for large series of parts that can vary from sports helmets to ribs for aircraft structures like ailerons. Because of its simplicity and low manufacturing cost, the range of parts that are produced with this process is still increasing.

The problem with rubber forming still is the long “trial and error” period that is needed, preliminary to the production. This “trial and error” trajectory involves both optimizing the process parameters and optimizing the rubber tool. For parts that are difficult to form, regarding wrinkling, also the use of a blankholder should be considered.

Conventional blankholders are based on uncontrollable spring forces and therefore it costs a lot of production cycles to find the optimum blankholder configuration. The purpose of this paper is to show the effect of the blankholder configuration on wrinkling and to show the interaction between Drape, blankholder configuration and the “trial and error” trajectory.

MATERIALS

The material used during this research is CETEX continuous glass fiber reinforced PPS. The glass fabric was SS0303, an 8H satin weave. The material was delivered as an 8-ply laminate with a quasi-isotropic build-up, which was cut to blanks of 50x60 cm. The SS0303 fabric was chosen because of its high fiber density of 220 fibers/10 cm. It is a very closed fabric, which means that wrinkles occur sooner than with a more open fabric. This will enable the investigation of the use of the blankholder to prevent fiber wrinkling.

The rubber used for rubber forming is silastic M silicone rubber. The maximum work temperature is 250°C, but it can withstand 320°C for a very short time.

RUBBER FORMING

Figure 1 shows the principle of the rubber forming process. The blank of continuous fiber reinforced thermoplastic is loaded into some kind of transport device, usually a blankholder, after which the material is heated in an infrared oven with double sided heating. When the desired material temperature is reached, rapid transport to the press (1) takes place. Finally, pressure is applied to consolidate the material (2).

Figure 1: Principle of rubber forming

Figure 3: Fabric deformations in the helmet at a maximum shearing angle of 40° (left: front view, right: top view).

BLANKHOLDER CONFIGURATION

The conventional blankholders currently being used, work with spring forces and pins (see figure 4). A steel frame is used to fix the tooling into the press. Holes are drilled in the blank for the pins. The pins are fixed onto a steel plate, which is able to move over the steel frame. The forces F_1 and F_3 on the springs determine the blankholder forces on the material, F_2 and F_4 . The position of the pins and the angle of the force α can be changed.

Figure 4: Principle of conventional blankholders.

Since it is not possible to control the blankholder forces when a conventional blankholder is used and the magnitude of the force appeared to be of great influence on wrinkling, the new smart blankholder was developed (figure 5). The blankholder exists of 10 pneumatic actuators mounted on a steel frame. The steel frame can be clamped in the conventional transfer clamps of the press. The frame with actuators and laminate moves through the infrared oven to the press and during pressing it remains in the press. Since the frame travels through the oven, all actuators, tubes and connectors are isolated with glass mats, covered by aluminum foil.

Figure 5: Smart blankholder.

The actuators have a maximum stroke of 20 cm each and a force range of 90-720 N, which is regulated by a pressure valve. The control system for individual control of the actuators is still under development and not used in the research described in this paper. Consequently, the actuators are simultaneously controlled. Figure 6 shows the freedom of movement of the actuators.

The choice for the type of clamping of the laminate is of influence on the effect of the blankholder. When a pin with a small diameter is used as attachment to the laminate, the blankholder force will act very locally. The pin goes through the laminate and the surrounding material melts during heating. During this research the material is clamped in between two steel plates, tightened with a bolt, which also goes through the laminate. The steel plates act as a heat sink, thus creating a so-called “cold zone”, wherein the material does not melt and as a result no fabric deformations can occur. The choice for the use of this clamping method was made because there appeared to be a large area within the helmet, where critical fabric deformations occur, considering the Drape analysis. By making use of the steel plates, the blankholder force covers a larger number of fiber bundles than in case pins are used and, therefore, this is more effective to prevent wrinkling in this specific case.

Figure 6: Freedom of movement for a) cylinder and b) Clamp

EXPERIMENTAL

First of all two helmets were pressed without the use of the smart blankholder. The blank was clamped in the existing transfer clamps of the press (see figure 7). As a result the clamped part of the laminate remains cold and deformations of the fabric are limited.

Figure 7: Laminate clamped in the conventional transfer clamps.

The deformation of a laminate during rubber forming is dependant on the fabric, the viscosity of the matrix, the material temperature, the die temperature, friction in the tooling, pressure and press speed. All these parameters were kept constant, except for the blankholder force. Table 1 gives an overview of the process parameters for all press cycles. During the heating phase of cycles 1 and 2 it became clear that the heating time was set too low to achieve the desired temperature of $325 \pm 5^\circ\text{C}$. A die temperature of 160°C is recommended to achieve the maximum degree of crystallinity of the PPS [3]. The test set-up is shown in figure 8, with the rubber die fixed to the upper press plate and the heated aluminum die fixed on the bottom press plate.

Table 1: Process parameters for the rubber forming of glass reinforced PPS helmets.

Cycle	Blankholder	Product no.	T (°C)	P (bar)	T _{die} (°C)	Press time (sec)	Blankholder force (N)
1	-	-	307	42	160	30	-
2	-	-	312	42	160	30	-
3	+	BHH01	330	42	160	30	190
4	+	BHH02	335	42	161	30	190
5	+	BHH03	330	42	160	30	279
6	+	BHH04	325	42	160	30	534
7	+	BHH05	325	42	160	30	445

The blankholder configuration was based on the drape analysis and the size of the blank. Only 4 of the 10 cylinders were needed and their position is sketched in figure 9 and was not changed. The effect of the blankholder force on wrinkling was investigated. When comparing products BHH01 and BHH02 with the products that were pressed without blankholder, it appeared that the large wrinkle in the front side of the helmet already became much smaller. Increasing the blankholder forces resulted in smaller wrinkles in general. A blankholder force of 190 N. appeared to have little effect on wrinkling. However, for higher forces the wrinkles became smaller and some wrinkles that were present in products BHH01 and 02 were vanished when the blankholder force was increased to 445 N – 534 N. The effect of the blankholder on wrinkling is shown in figure 10.

Figure 8: Test set-up

Figure 9: Position of the cylinders

10a) Clamped in conventional transfer clamps

10b) BHH01
Blankholder force = 190 N

10c) BHH03
Blankholder force = 279 N

10d) BHH05
Blankholder force = 445 N

- 10e) BHH04
Blankholder force = 534 N

Figure 10: photos of rubber formed helmets.

- a) conventional transfer clamps
- b) Product BHH01
- c) Product BHH03
- d) Product BHH05
- e) Product BHH04

The improvements with increasing blankholder forces can be seen in the circled areas.

CONCLUSION

When Drape is used to determine the deformability of a fabric during rubber forming and the areas where critical shearing angles occur with respect to wrinkling, the position of the blankholder forces can be determined. The need for a blankholder depends on the type of fabric used and the laminate build-up.

The smart blankholder can be used to reduce and avoid wrinkling. It appeared that increasing the blankholder force results in smaller wrinkles and also the number of wrinkles is reduced. For complex parts it will be necessary to regulate the pressure in the cylinders separately. Also, the forces should be coupled to the press speed of the deformation stroke.

When the blankholder forces could be introduced within Drape the optimum blankholder configuration can already be obtained before processing. When it appears that wrinkling can not be prevented, the decision might be made to choose another material or to change the shape of the part to be formed. The trajectory of “trial and error” can drastically be reduced in this way.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This research project is made possible by the support of Ten Cate Advanced Composites through the input of their technical knowledge and material supply.

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